

Learning from Long-Term Care practices
for the European Care Strategy

NATIONAL REPORT DENMARK: THE MEANINGS OF SUSTAINABILITY IN LTC IN DENMARK

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Contents

The meanings of Sustainability in LTC in Denmark	4
Brief summary.....	4
1. Definitions	4
2. Boundaries.....	5
3. Resources.....	5
4. Stakeholders and Governance.....	6
5. Territorial Differentiation.....	7
6. Debates, Strategies	7
Literature	10
Annex 1 Expenditure per elderly above the age of 67 in fixed 2019 prices.....	11

The meanings of Sustainability in LTC in Denmark

Brief summary

There is no firm definition of what sustainability in Long-Term care in Denmark is. The debates revolve around the ability to finance long-term care as well as having the necessary manpower to do so. Thereby, the discussions also relate to how the expected demographic transitions will influence the need for long-term care in Denmark, including the degree of healthy ageing.

1. Definitions

There is no clear and single definition of sustainability within and with regard to long-term care. The concept of sustainability can be looked at from many angles e.g. social, economic as well as environmental. Despite of this, both in the public debate as well as in our stakeholder interviews people seem to mostly be talking about the social and economic aspects, and hereunder the concern of available economic resources as well as the necessary qualified staff available.

Historically, the focus has been that there have not sufficient economic resources. This can also be witnessed in the interviews done on the matter, particularly among municipalities but also other stakeholders such as trade unions, users and different interest groups. In recent years the municipalities have been compensated for the change in inflation and the demographic composition. This compensation is an average for all municipalities, which might imply that some municipalities have difficulties in continuing the existing level of services while others might be able to increase the level.

An issue present in more or less all interviews has pointed towards the risk of lack of qualified staffs in the years to come as a consequence of the demographic changes with many today working in the long-term care sector retiring and an increase in the number of elderly in need of care. As a stakeholder stated: It is breaking down, so overall, the system is not sustainable because supply and demand cannot be met. There are more and more elderly people, there is more and more need, and there are fewer and fewer to care for them, and resources are not being provided to the necessary extent."

Projections on the need for long-term care is difficult to calculate as this involves discussions on the level of services, but also how healthy ageing can influence the sustainability of care for the elderly in the Danish welfare state. Still, it is with regard to the future sustainability the most salient issue.

2. Boundaries

There are no differences and clear boundaries given that the element is highly normative about what level of care should be provided. However, at the same time how technology can influence the need for staff is an issue, such as using different technologies to do the cleaning, being in contact with the health care staff, etc, which may all have an impact on the need for resources.

The degree of active ageing might also reduce the need for staff, while at the same time the expected increase in the number of elderly, especially above the age of 80 with dementia implies new pressure and risks related to the long-term care system.

As indicated above in section 1 there are variations across municipalities of what they spend on long-term care, see also Annex 1 and the next section.

There can further be boundaries to other parts of the welfare state's spending – such as issues related to healthy living and use of welfare technology.

3. Resources

There are no clear indicators of the issue of sustainability. The main aspects are related to what the change in cost will be if the level of services remain at the current level and how then the growth in public sector spending will have to be. In the long-term estimates the present government has included that the welfare state's cost to long-term care will in real terms follow the change in the number of elderly people in the years to come.

In Annex 1 is in fixed 2019 prices presented data for the spending per elderly above the age of 67 of every municipality. This shows that the level has been stable since 2019, but also that there are variations across municipalities with some spending more than others and some with increase and

some with decrease. This can reflect local priorities and not necessarily indicate anything about sustainability.

The core future issue of the risk of lack of qualified human resources is dealt with in a report from the Ministry of Finance (Finansministeriet 2023), which tries to estimate the possible lack of manpower resources by 2035 for different types of workers in relation to care and health. This due to that the demographic transitions imply a need to get more workers in the future in Denmark tasked with the delivery of welfare services, and especially in relation to long-term care and health care. Notably with regard to social care workers (SOSU-hjælper and SOSU-assistent) there can be an issue of lack of workforce. As argued in an interview, already today a large number of staff in the elderly care sector is without formal qualifications. The ministry's analysis is based upon a stylized prognosis using the age of employees today, expected retirement age and the expected increase in newly educated people within these different areas. It can be questioned whether this is a sufficiently precise way of estimating the need, also considering possible changes in technology and the healthy ageing. Nevertheless, it has been a strong issue in the interviews with stakeholders that lack of workers can influence the sustainability of the long-term care in Denmark.

4. Stakeholders and Governance

There is no other stakeholders or governance issue with regard to this issue than there is in relation to other long-term care issues in Denmark, e.g. it is state, municipalities, employees and users that are central. The main rules are decided by the parliament; however, the implementation takes place within the local municipalities who have options to prioritize between different welfare state areas, including the service for the elderly. Even if municipalities have the right to decide on a municipality income tax, the overall economic situation for municipalities is dealt with in yearly agreements with the Ministry of Finance. Thus, it is within these boundaries that the level of spending and taxation in a municipality has to be seen. Here there are often different viewpoints between the central and local level of what there should be available of economic resources, including the level of block grant from the state to the municipalities.

There is constantly an ongoing discussion whether the state's block grant to municipalities is fair or whether there should be transferred more to some municipalities with lower average income and a demographic composition that can be more challenging.

Still, as also mentioned above, it might be difficult to know whether differences are due to variations in economic resources or reflect the degree of freedom municipalities have to decide on the level of services within most of the welfare areas they are responsible for.

5. Territorial Differentiation

There is no specific territorial differentiation besides what the overall issue of equality in access to long-term care across the municipalities informs about. A future issue might be that the demographic transition varies across municipalities so that some might have bigger challenges than others, cf. also the issue about the rules for the state block grants to municipalities as indicated above. Still, the Danish system with support to municipalities through block-grants is part of the way to ensure that there is at least partly taken care of the different economic local challenges of the change in demography and income wealth across municipalities in Denmark.

6. Debates, Strategies

There is a number of issues related to the debates on the sustainability of long-term care. This revolves around the ability to finance due to the increasing number of elderly who most likely will be in need of care, but also as mentioned above that there might be a lack of qualified staff.

The ability to finance long-term care is a highly normative issue as this will depend on how to prioritize between different parts of the welfare states and the willingness to pay taxes and duties in the future (Greve 2024b; 2024a). Thus, this question can't be answered simply by an analysis of factors influencing the development, albeit this can be an indicator of the expected future need for resources to the area. However, the Danish economy is overall solid, but still, it will be an issue for the political decision makers to find out what they are willing to pay for in the years to come, including at what level of quality of care and quality of care work, which will also have an impact on the sustainability. Furthermore, the fact that there always will be an issue of cost to this area and cost to other welfare services. It is mentioned by some of the stakeholders that there is an issue concerning the availability of the necessary economic resources. In relation to the longer term issues it is the following point that is the central issue.

The expected future lack of manpower due to the demographic changes with more people leaving the labour market than entering it as by many stakeholders mentioned as a very important issue. The lack of manpower might at least partly be solved by employing more people full time than is the case today, earlier start of the education and a reduction in sickness. There is no detailed information on what necessary and possible instruments might be used to ensure that this will be the case in order to ensure a higher labour force. However, elements include better quality of work, including higher levels of influence and for some less work during nights and weekends (Indenrigs- og Sundhedsministeriets Benchmarkingenhed 2024). As some stakeholders also mention, the issue relates to the need for higher wages as well as better recognition of the value of the job, especially in order to make younger people choose an education within the field and thereby help ensuring a higher level of educated staff within the sector.

An analysis has pointed towards options and barriers to get people to work full-time (Lauritzen 2024), as getting more to work full-time would reduce both the need for finding other persons, but also reduce the future risk of lack of staff. The analysis is based upon a qualitative case study with interviews in five municipalities. The report argues that the job's physical and psychological challenges are one of the reasons for working part-time. Another barrier to get people to work full-time is that people then will have to work more during weekends and this is seen as a barrier for combining work and family life. Change in the organisation of work to ensure that the workload is spread more evenly across daytime might be a way to get people to work full time. Teams might also be a way if this increases the quality of working life. At the same time, wage levels do not seem to be a barrier for changing from part-time to full-time.

The issue of wages has also been an issue discussed in Denmark including whether higher wages would make it possible to ensure that more workers could be attracted to work within the sector, to continue to work after reaching retirement age and also take an education qualifying for working within the area.

A tripartite agreement¹ in the autumn of 2023 included support to social workers within the long-term care sector as a way to, as argued, implying a better recognition of the work done, but also as an

¹ [Treparsaftale om løn og arbejdsvilkår \(bm.dk\)](https://www.bm.dk/da/nyheder/2023/10/13-trepartsaftale-om-lon-og-arbejdsvilkar), accessed the 6th September 2024. A tripartite agreement is between employers, employees and the state. This tripartite was at the same time discussed as this was a deviation from that wages are an issue to cope with in the collective agreements.

instrument which can help making it more attractive to work in the sector. This, in turn, should also make it more attractive to take an education in order to work within the long-term care sector in Denmark. Whether this is sufficient is still an open question. The tripartite agreement was further seen as in contradiction with the autonomy of the labour market partners to agree on the collective agreements. Thus, if wage is an issue, then it will most likely be an element that the labour market partners will be responsible for finding a solution to, also bearing in mind that there can also be other public sector employees who want higher income and better working conditions.

Use of welfare technology is also mentioned in the interviews as an element expected to help in ensuring sustainability as this might reduce the need for staff, including also options for elderly to be able “to stay as long as possible in their own life” and then be able better to take care of themselves. Welfare technology is already used in a number of activities within long-term care. It is difficult to estimate how much and what technology (including AI) will be able to reduce the pressure for more workers within the sector as a central part of the job might to lesser degree than other types of jobs on the labour market be changed by welfare technology.

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Annex 1 Expenditure per elderly above the age of 67 in fixed 2019 prices

	Municipality number	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Københavns Kommune	101	65.387	66.714	65.381	66.755	63.765	60.464
Frederiksberg Kommune	147	48.716	52.916	53.808	51.969	51.296	52.146
Ballerup Kommune	151	44.850	45.940	50.793	47.999	47.306	49.657
Brøndby Kommune	153	61.762	59.228	58.993	58.614	57.836	60.048
Dragør Kommune	155	44.667	44.198	43.004	42.176	43.804	44.174
Gentofte Kommune	157	52.385	54.174	53.890	52.694	53.765	54.176
Gladsaxe Kommune	159	54.425	54.176	54.613	55.309	56.115	55.769
Glostrup Kommune	161	53.204	55.316	54.251	54.470	53.678	54.010
Herlev Kommune	163	48.944	50.889	50.478	52.357	55.118	51.221
Albertslund Kommune	165	53.713	56.764	59.242	57.756	55.553	55.045
Hvidovre Kommune	167	56.964	59.240	61.832	59.569	58.810	58.259
Høje-Taastrup Kommune	169	41.724	42.015	43.367	41.667	44.872	44.939
Lyngby-Taarbæk Kommune	173	57.210	54.519	56.766	57.184	54.424	51.129
Rødovre Kommune	175	61.082	62.680	60.562	63.284	63.294	59.717
Ishøj Kommune	183	44.959	44.236	47.012	51.893	52.949	51.419
Tårnby Kommune	185	49.217	52.929	53.136	54.044	52.570	48.382
Vallensbæk Kommune	187	35.867	37.650	36.033	39.325	41.876	46.364

Furesø Kommune	190	38.784	41.105	40.829	42.302	42.830	41.718
Allerød Kommune	201	38.895	41.937	42.001	41.193	41.038	39.395
Fredensborg Kommune	210	37.780	40.409	40.867	42.863	43.080	44.527
Helsingør Kommune	217	43.789	48.142	45.939	45.768	45.997	46.045
Hillerød Kommune	219	44.801	45.398	44.979	45.158	44.919	43.521
Hørsholm Kommune	223	37.756	42.758	44.007	43.584	42.647	41.575
Rudersdal Kommune	230	50.253	51.798	51.954	51.775	51.619	49.502
Egedal Kommune	240	33.080	38.487	38.775	40.461	40.809	40.339
Frederikssund Kommune	250	41.120	43.115	43.340	42.797	43.228	41.559
Halsnæs Kommune	260	38.694	39.258	38.308	38.365	37.165	36.578
Gribskov Kommune	270	41.236	38.637	39.274	40.542	43.108	42.430
Bornholms Kommune	400	48.297	45.893	45.743	45.163	44.582	42.628
Greve Kommune	253	34.042	37.773	40.624	41.897	41.771	43.456
Køge Kommune	259	44.432	45.245	45.702	46.763	47.606	45.227
Roskilde Kommune	265	39.938	43.072	43.685	39.294	37.877	41.085
Solrød Kommune	269	37.026	39.556	38.752	40.038	41.046	40.941
Odsherred Kommune	306	37.904	40.144	41.334	39.078	39.295	37.525
Holbæk Kommune	316	35.692	35.506	39.002	39.299	38.967	37.636
Faxe Kommune	320	37.525	40.160	38.779	41.849	39.802	40.848
Kalundborg Kommune	326	36.887	37.969	38.587	39.297	39.263	38.455

Ringsted Kommune	329	41.911	40.317	45.801	47.390	44.580	41.971
Slagelse Kommune	330	43.611	45.373	46.331	45.774	42.963	43.672
Stevns Kommune	336	35.243	38.514	37.723	36.330	38.434	37.240
Sorø Kommune	340	41.747	42.785	44.203	44.149	42.831	41.455
Lejre Kommune	350	36.068	34.811	34.032	36.672	34.625	34.665
Lolland Kommune	360	46.667	47.631	46.670	45.455	44.621	42.554
Næstved Kommune	370	39.652	42.748	42.652	43.727	41.969	40.829
Guldborgsund Kommune	376	40.909	40.402	42.894	39.583	38.256	38.493
Vordingborg Kommune	390	39.862	40.643	42.681	44.525	40.589	43.121
Middelfart Kommune	410	36.002	38.596	40.034	39.464	37.949	36.475
Assens Kommune	420	36.715	36.082	37.034	36.928	37.930	36.101
Faaborg-Midtfyn Kommune	430	39.116	38.697	39.477	37.865	38.805	37.819
Kerteminde Kommune	440	40.220	44.341	45.102	44.012	41.202	41.388
Nyborg Kommune	450	40.053	39.851	40.248	42.417	43.985	40.998
Odense Kommune	461	41.962	43.969	43.178	44.770	43.287	43.112
Svendborg Kommune	479	42.478	44.186	44.507	42.639	41.212	38.903
Nordfyns Kommune	480	35.578	35.936	38.200	38.830	38.015	37.451
Langeland Kommune	482	56.502	55.914	55.300	54.729	53.549	45.532
Ærø Kommune	492	49.136	48.731	49.265	47.142	47.804	44.697
Haderslev Kommune	510	40.986	42.586	42.804	43.598	43.208	43.695

Billund Kommune	530	49.667	48.720	46.815	47.636	47.463	46.794
Sønderborg Kommune	540	42.631	43.902	44.830	44.154	43.692	45.796
Tønder Kommune	550	42.319	42.814	41.079	40.960	41.398	38.422
Esbjerg Kommune	561	48.401	46.594	46.265	45.630	45.020	46.787
Fanø Kommune	563	33.482	35.586	37.235	36.942	43.461	39.215
Varde Kommune	573	41.493	43.329	42.805	41.903	41.341	38.776
Vejen Kommune	575	43.937	42.868	44.838	45.546	44.573	42.166
Aabenraa Kommune	580	40.813	40.270	42.472	43.768	42.583	43.414
Fredericia Kommune	607	48.890	49.077	49.293	48.783	47.673	45.678
Kolding Kommune	621	43.746	43.581	43.387	43.839	42.990	42.928
Vejle Kommune	630	38.902	38.720	38.176	38.144	38.053	37.443
Horsens Kommune	615	41.462	42.921	43.738	44.460	43.484	42.732
Herning Kommune	657	37.581	38.359	38.441	39.586	38.623	38.534
Holstebro Kommune	661	40.334	40.745	40.840	38.830	37.293	35.783
Lemvig Kommune	665	38.363	38.363	37.427	39.918	37.527	36.790
Struer Kommune	671	41.053	41.398	39.781	40.062	37.666	36.245
Syddjurs Kommune	706	34.909	38.311	37.112	38.119	36.276	33.828
Norrdjurs Kommune	707	39.687	42.052	43.493	44.309	43.614	42.952
Favrskov Kommune	710	37.816	37.817	38.016	39.101	37.499	38.261
Odder Kommune	727	41.196	43.576	45.246	40.303	38.900	39.926

Randers Kommune	730	45.125	46.435	49.392	49.207	49.081	47.454
Silkeborg Kommune	740	45.623	42.807	42.207	42.015	40.774	39.712
Samsø Kommune	741	49.018	50.990	49.579	50.035	49.102	45.670
Skanderborg Kommune	746	42.031	40.036	40.865	38.759	39.061	37.471
Aarhus Kommune	751	44.716	45.699	44.410	44.136	43.408	43.993
Ikast-Brande Kommune	756	44.897	42.476	41.448	41.602	43.822	42.118
Ringkøbing-Skjern Kommune	760	38.988	40.515	43.155	42.556	42.021	40.219
Hedensted Kommune	766	37.723	37.665	36.598	37.668	38.137	38.873
Skive Kommune	779	41.264	41.862	41.133	40.154	40.782	41.455
Viborg Kommune	791	41.983	42.498	42.980	42.092	41.761	40.728
Morsø Kommune	773	51.881	50.829	52.201	50.949	48.740	43.792
Thisted Kommune	787	46.220	45.050	45.339	44.130	44.310	43.091
Brønderslev Kommune	810	42.242	43.257	43.998	42.946	44.497	41.575
Frederikshavn Kommune	813	40.511	41.326	41.832	42.139	42.001	39.419
Vesthimmerlands Kommune	820	42.970	44.685	44.516	44.086	42.279	43.342
Læsø Kommune	825	55.577	52.631	55.904	57.331	56.581	50.064
Rebild Kommune	840	43.338	46.257	47.513	46.906	45.286	41.701
Mariagerfjord Kommune	846	41.358	42.426	41.315	42.937	44.025	38.983
Jammerbugt Kommune	849	38.792	39.113	38.668	38.482	38.980	37.881
Aalborg Kommune	851	47.844	47.986	48.285	47.916	47.995	47.430

Hjørring Kommune	860	39.609	40.999	41.678	42.553	41.445	40.145
Gennemsnit (27)		44.264	45.183	45.453	45.423	44.771	43.940

Source: Indenrigs- og Sundhedsministeriet d. 19. december 2024,
<https://www.noegletal.dk/noegletal/nctrlman>